

D8.5: Promotional Video, third batch

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0.2	13/04/2025	Rigmor Baraas, Rose bernabe	Comments on the 1st draft of the voice over
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This deliverable is awaiting approval from European Commission

1. Aim of the 1st promotional video

Within the framework of dissemination and communication activities for XR4Human, and in collaboration with all partners, WP8 developed the project’s third promotional video. In general, the purpose of XR4Human’s promotional videos is to support the project’s dissemination and communication efforts, as outlined in the Grant Agreement. Specifically, the third promotional video presents XR4Human’s main outcomes and highlights the project’s contribution to the ethical and human-centered development of XR technologies.

The video is primarily targeted at XR developers but is also relevant for users and researchers, as it showcases all project outcomes, each addressing different stakeholders. As with the first and second promotional videos, the content combines images of real people using XR applications and devices with animated elements.

The video will be made available on the project website and YouTube channel, and it will also be shared through the project’s social media channels.

2. Video Content and Key Visuals

This section provides an overview of the third XR4Human promotional video, including its content and key visual elements. Selected screenshots from the video are included to illustrate how the project communicates its mission and outcomes in a visually engaging way.

The video were carefully designed to align with XR4Human’s distinctive visual identity, consistently using the project’s official colors, fonts, and icons for a cohesive and recognizable look. Vibrant visuals and imagery related to VR, AR, and XR technologies were deliberately employed to make the content both appealing and user-friendly. The combination of narrative and visuals demonstrates XR4Human’s approach to promoting ethical, inclusive, and interoperable XR technologies to developers, researchers, and users alike, while maintaining a consistent and engaging aesthetic throughout.

The video opens by welcoming viewers to the XR4Human project with an acknowledgment to our funders (EC). It emphasizes that, after years of collaboration, research, and engagement, XR4Human’s outcomes are now available for use and further development.

Figure 1: Introductory screen of the video

One key element of the video is the **XR Code of Conduct**. This section highlights the growing ethical challenges in XR and presents the Code as a living guide for responsible and inclusive XR development, helping developers create more ethical virtual worlds. The video also showcases the **Interoperability Guidelines**, designed to break barriers between platforms and enable seamless XR experiences across devices and applications.

Figure 2: XR4Human Code of Conduct

Figure 3: XR4Human Interoperability Guidelines

To address gaps in regulation, the video presents the **Regulatory Gap Analysis**, which identifies areas where policies need adaptation to protect users, foster innovation, and ensure a safe XR ecosystem. For end users, the video emphasizes the **Educational Toolbox**, providing guides and resources to empower safe and responsible interaction with XR technologies.

Figure 4: The Regulatory Gap Analysis

The **XR4Human Experience Library** is highlighted next, showcasing real-world examples and best practices in XR development, and encouraging the community to share experiences that help shape the future of XR. The **XR4Human Forum** is also introduced as a platform for ongoing reflection, engagement, discussions, and co-creation among developers, researchers, and users.

Figure 5: Key Features of the XR4Human Experience Library

Figure 6: The XR4Human Forum and interaction with stakeholders

The major focus of the video is the **XR4Human Rating Repository**, a central platform that consolidates all project outcomes, including Ethics, Interoperability, and Legal/Policy documents. The Repository features tools to rate XR applications based on ethical, safety, and technical standards and provides guidance on implementing the Code of Conduct, submitting XR applications, engaging in discussions, and collaborating with the XR4Human community. The Rating Repository is illustrated through the visualization of a real human navigating its features, highlighting its structure and accessibility.

Figure 7: The front page of the XR4Human Rating Repository

Figure 8: The guide for rating XR applications

Figure 9: Repository of resources for rating XR applications

The video concludes by reinforcing XR4Human as a foundation for the future of XR, offering tools, knowledge, and insights for everyone to use, improve, and build upon. Viewers are invited to join the XR community through the project website, forum, and social media channels.

Figure 10: XR4Human project logo and official communication channels

3. Communication of the 3rd promotional video

The video will serve as a communication and dissemination tool to promote the XR4Human project, highlighting its main outputs and contributions to the XR community of practice.

It will be shared online via the project’s website, the XR4Human YouTube channel, and social media platforms. WP8 will provide all project partners with the video URL to facilitate its dissemination through existing networks, including partners’ social media accounts. Additionally, the video can be used at events and conferences (e.g., embedded in presentations or played on laptops/screens) to showcase the project’s key objectives, procedures, and methodology in a visually engaging and accessible manner.

The primary aim of the third promotional video is to communicate the comprehensive achievements of the XR4Human project and to encourage the XR community to adopt the project’s outcomes and further develop them. This video will be featured on the project’s website homepage and shared across XR4Human’s social media channels. It will also serve as a key resource for presentations at the XR4Human Code of Conduct conference and, following the conclusion of the project, at other conferences, meetings, and events where a comprehensive overview of XR4Human’s outcomes is required.

Tailored for diverse stakeholders, the video highlights the project’s main goals, its contributions to the ethical and human-centered development of XR technologies, the developed tools and guidelines. By doing so, it provides a holistic understanding of the XR4Human project’s impact and significance.

4. Deviations from DoA

No Deviations from DoA.

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